

Prototyping an AI-Driven Cognitive Coordinator for Mapping User Intent to Trustworthiness in 6G Networks

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Abstract—The transition to sixth-generation (6G) mobile networks envisions a fully software-defined, cloud-native architecture that spans from central clouds to far-edge micro-data centers. While SDN, NFV, and edge computing unlock unprecedented agility and service diversity, they also enlarge the attack surface and elevate risks to confidentiality, integrity, and availability. Existing security measures in 5G remain fragmented—separate efforts address privacy, resilience, reliability, security, or safety in isolation—and lack a unified metric for end-to-end trust. This paper introduces trustworthiness as a holistic, multi-dimensional metric that aggregates user-specified requirements across five pillars—Safety, Security, Privacy, Resilience, and Reliability—into a single Level of Trustworthiness (LoTw). A proof-of-concept prototype of an AI-driven Cognitive Coordinator that ingests user intents via a chatbot and maps them to LoTw with BERT-based regression heads is presented, validating the proposed formal definition of Trustworthiness towards a truly user-centric and trustworthy 6G network.

Keywords— 6G, Trustworthiness, User-centric, User-intent, Security, AI, ML.

I. INTRODUCTION

The sixth generation (6G) of mobile networks is poised to deliver unprecedented levels of flexibility, performance, and service diversity by embracing a fully software-defined architecture. Building on the successes of software-defined networking (SDN), network function virtualization (NFV), and mobile edge computing, 6G envisions a cloud-native, programmable fabric that spans from central clouds to far-edge micro-data centers. This softwarization enables rapid service instantiation, fine-grained resource allocation, and dynamic network slicing tailored to individual application requirements [1]. By decoupling control and user planes and treating network capabilities as reconfigurable software components, operators and third parties alike can introduce new functionalities without the delays inherent in hardware rollout.

However, the very features that make 6G agile and extensible also multiply its attack surface and elevate security risks. Virtualization layers, management APIs, and orchestrators represent potential entry points for adversaries aiming to compromise confidentiality, integrity, or

availability. Malicious actors can exploit software bugs, misconfigurations, or weak authentication to mount DDoS attacks, inject false data, or seize control of critical network elements [2]. As 6G caters to safety-critical domains—industrial automation, vehicular communications, remote surgery—the cost of successful breaches escalates dramatically. Consequently, securing softwarized infrastructures has become an imperative, driving research into targeted countermeasures that harden each layer of the network stack.

To date, disparate strands of work have tackled individual aspects of 6G security. Privacy-preserving schemes employ federated learning and differential privacy to protect user data at the edge. Reliability studies focus on redundancy mechanisms and service-level agreement (SLA) enforcement to guarantee uninterrupted connectivity. Resilience research devises self-healing and automated fail-over strategies to sustain operation under faults or attacks. Classical security solutions address encryption, key management, and intrusion detection to defend against unauthorized access. Safety-oriented approaches further ensure that control loops in cyber-physical systems respond predictably even amid network anomalies. Each of these efforts contributes a vital piece to the puzzle of trustworthy 6G operation.

Despite the depth of specialized solutions, the lack of a unified framework for measuring and governing overall network security remains a critical gap. Metrics devised for privacy, resilience, reliability, security, or safety are often defined in isolation and optimized independently, leading to conflicting trade-offs when deployed in tandem. For instance, strengthening encryption may degrade latency-sensitive services, while aggressive fail-over policies can inflate resource consumption and undermine cost efficiency. Network operators and service providers thus lack a holistic yardstick that captures the combined impact of multiple safeguards on end-to-end trust.

In this work, we introduce trustworthiness as an overarching, multi-dimensional metric that quantifies a 6G system’s ability to meet user-defined expectations for safety, security, privacy, resilience, and reliability. By aggregating dimension-specific scores through a mathematically grounded weighting and calibration model, we offer a single coherent

indicator that accounts for user intent, resource constraints, and operational realities. Trustworthiness enables network coordinators to navigate the complex trade-space between competing objectives and to orchestrate security-oriented network functions in a closed-loop, adaptive manner.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II surveys prior work on holistic security metrics and intent-driven orchestration in beyond-5G/6G networks. Section III formalizes the concept of trustworthiness in 6G, defining its five core dimensions and their relation to tenant-specific intents. In Section IV, we present our proof-of-concept implementation of the AI-driven Cognitive Coordinator, detailing its regression, reasoning, and orchestration components. Section V evaluates CoCo’s training process, dataset characteristics, and real-world performance metrics. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper and outlines directions for future research.

II. BACKGROUND ON HOLISTIC SECURITY METRICS FOR USER-CENTRIC B5G/6G NETWORKS

Several recent efforts have sought to define comprehensive security metrics for 6G that transcend isolated layers or domains. Abdelrazek et al. [3] introduce a finite state-machine model that captures the security life cycle of network functions and identifies three essential metrics—attack surface exposure, vulnerability impact, and security control effectiveness. By hierarchically aggregating these metrics at node, domain, and network levels, they derive an overall security score that can drive intent-based automation and zero-touch configuration in 5G/6G environments.

Ericsson’s white paper on 6G security drivers [4] underscores the need for a holistic approach that integrates both communication and computation security. It argues that emerging 6G use cases—from immersive extended reality to zero-energy IoT—demand renewed threat analyses and new controls, and calls for a risk-based security posture built on open standards and operational resilience.

Farooq et al. [5] survey the expanded attack surface inherent in 6G’s open, distributed, and user-centric SBA. They highlight vulnerabilities in APIs, pervasive cloud-native functions, and decentralized architectures, and propose blockchain and Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) as foundational technologies for decentralized trust management, selective disclosure, and immutable auditability in 6G core networks.

While these works advance holistic security metrics, they often remain detached from orchestration frameworks capable of translating high-level intents into enforceable configurations [6]. Intent-Based Networking (IBN) research addresses this gap by mapping user or tenant policies to automated service deployments [7]. The Hexa-X-II initiative [8] details ten technological enablers for multi-stakeholder, intent-driven E2E service management—ranging from intent translation and closed-loop coordination to intent conflict resolution and human-machine interfaces—demonstrating how intents can orchestrate resources across the edge-cloud continuum and multiple administrative domains.

Complementing IBN, user-centric orchestration frameworks harness Digital Twin (DT) abstractions to model and predict per-user service requirements. Zhou et al. [9] propose a DT-based framework for immersive communications in 6G, where each user’s DT encapsulates

personalized data attributes and network models, enabling tailored resource management and real-time orchestration aligned with unique quality-of-experience demands.

Collectively, these studies lay the groundwork for a unified, intent-driven orchestration paradigm in 6G—one that integrates multi-dimensional security metrics (safety, security, privacy, resilience, reliability) into closed-loop coordination engines, thus delivering coherent, user-centric trustworthiness across SDN/NFV-enabled networks.

III. TRUSTWORTHINESS IN 6G NETWORKS

A. Qualitative Definition of Trustworthiness

The 6G vision for an open, distributed and user-centric evolution of the current Service Based Architecture (SBA) core network creates many security challenges and risks. The disaggregated heterogeneous cloud continuum (i.e., distributed cloud system with many stakeholders located in different regions, while private, public, or hybrid clouds are considered for the formation of the continuum), in conjunction with softwarization and IT-based infrastructure operations, sets the stage for risks and challenges to trustworthiness in the 6G era.

The existing 5G security architecture is adaptable to a centralized network architecture, and in 5G, trust connections between network parts are created at the protocol level, rather than involving device and network behaviour. In the envisioned 6G ecosystem, trusted connections are critical for all parties involved, extending security and privacy to a more inclusive framework, such as trustworthiness, which should be assured as a native feature.

B. Trustworthiness and Trust Relation

Currently, IMT 2030 promotes trustworthiness as a new attribute for the 6G vision. In fact, numerous standard groups, including 3GPP, ETSI, and IEEE, have been working on trustworthiness issues.

Figure 1: 6G system Trustworthiness and tenant/user trust relationship

Meanwhile, the world’s main communications suppliers have explicitly underlined the importance of 6G trustworthiness in their 6G projects, proposals, and white papers. In addition, several scholars have produced technical papers on the definition, generation, protection, and optimization of trustworthiness. All of these suggests that trustworthiness will become an essential characteristic in 6G, but still, it remains confusing the use of trustworthiness and trust terms.

The most significant paradigm adjustments in the envisioned user-centric 6G system are the shift from a security-only focus to a broader scope of native trustworthiness, clarifying that the term "trustworthiness" refers to a holistic approach, including safety, security,

privacy, resilience and reliability as trustworthiness dimensions and properties. Moreover, a realistic solution to this trustworthiness challenge must recognize that all security measures (i.e., Safety, Security, Privacy, Resilience and Reliability) come at a cost in terms of usability, agility, or swiftness. As a result, the envisioned trustworthiness framework should provide a balance between the various dimensions/properties by dealing with a security-by-design approach, as well as a wide range of themes, such as the trust model and the application of a novel cognitive coordination component (e.g., Intent-based trustworthiness, based on Artificial Intelligence (AI) / Machine Learning (ML) techniques).

Considering that each tenant/user has different requirements in terms of trust level from a 6G system, it is created the need the 6G system to be capable of being adapted to the specific needs (i.e., trustworthiness level) that corresponds to the level of trust and requirements of each specific tenant/user. Therefore, the 6G system should not be only trustworthy in a static way, but it should become user-centric and capable of dynamically adapting the trustworthiness level to the trust level requirements of each tenant. The user-centric approach in 6G system allows for dedicated network services to be provided at the granularity of the user by configuring appropriately the 6G system (i.e., the core network functions) [6-7].

IV. PROOF OF CONCEPT IMPLEMENTATION OF AI-ASSISTED INTENT-BASED/USER-CENTRIC TRUSTWORTHINESS

A. High-Level Concept

In order to achieve this user-centric and intent-based driven dynamic trustworthiness configuration of a 6G system, in this paper we introduce a proof of concept implementation of an AI/ML-assisted coordination component, namely Cognitive Coordinator (CoCo). CoCo acts as an intent-handling function that comprehends sophisticated and abstract trust intent semantics (divided into the five trustworthiness dimensions/taxonomies of Safety, Security, Privacy, Resilience, and Reliability), calculates the ideal goal state of Level of Trustworthiness (LoTw) and organizes activities to transition the 6G system into a trustworthy state.

Figure 2: User-centric and AI-assisted coordination of 6G trustworthiness

The AI-assisted CoCo performs the process of mapping the trust-intent semantics received by the tenant/user into transition actions of the 6G system via configurations in the trustworthy dimensions. The Cognitive Coordinator (CoCo) is an internal intelligence component of the system that interfaces directly with the end user through a chatbot. It interprets user intents and translates them into adaptive configuration actions, enabling the 6G system to dynamically adjust its operational state according to the user's needs, who is the final recipient of the solution.

B. Proof of Concept Implementation of CoCo based on a Formal Definition of Trustworthiness

The PoC implementation of the CoCo comprises three core components:

1) Regression Component

The Regression Component serves as the initial processing stage within the Cognitive Coordinator pipeline. It ingests semantically parsed user trust expressions provided by a Large Language Model (LLM), which uses an Natural Language Processing (NLP) pipeline to convert raw natural language into structured representations aligned with the five trust dimensions: Safety, Security, Privacy, Resilience, and Reliability. Each user input sentence or keyword is associated with one or more Trust Functions (TFs) based on semantic similarity and classification logic. The complete workflow of this component is represented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Workflow for the calculation of the Non-calibrated level of trustworthiness.

To compute the preliminary, non-calibrated Level of Trustworthiness (nLoTw), this component employs a pre-trained Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) model, selected for its strong contextual embedding capabilities and generalizability across linguistic domains. On top of the shared BERT encoder, five specialized regression heads-one per Trust Function-are finetuned for the regression task. Each head outputs a continuous trustworthiness score $RG_{TF_j} \in [0,1]$, corresponding to the TF-specific trust demand inferred from the input. The number of sentences n_{TF_j} classified under each trust function $TF_j \in \{1,2,3,4,5\}$ and the total number of sentences N are used to define a dynamic weighting mechanism that reflects the distribution of user concerns. Instead of using simple frequency ratios, the CoCo model introduces a logarithmic-based weighting function that improves smoothness and mitigates sparsity effects:

$$W_{TF_j} = \frac{\log(1 + n_{TF_j})}{\sum_{j=1}^5 \log(e^{n_{TF_j}})}$$

This weight captures the proportional relevance of each TF in the user's intent profile. The non-calibrated Level of Trustworthiness (nLoTw) is then computed as the normalized weighted average of the TF-specific regression outputs:

$$nLoTw = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^5 W_{TF_j} R_{G_{TF_j}}}{\sum_{j=1}^5 W_{TF_j}} \cdot 100$$

The resulting score serves as the system's initial estimation of the overall trustworthiness requirement. This vectorized output encapsulates per-function demands and triggers downstream reasoning and orchestration logic. The modular design of this architecture allows for future extensibility-supporting the integration of domain-specific encoders, alternate transformer variants, or task-adaptive heads to improve generalization in evolving trust scenarios.

2) Reasoning Engine

The Reasoning Engine constitutes the context-aware calibration stage of the trust pipeline. Its primary function is to refine the non-calibrated trust (nLoTw) into a realistic and deployable calibrated trust level (cLoTw) by incorporating system-wide resource constraints into trust computation.

For each Trust Function, the regression-derived trust score is evaluated with respect to user information and real-time computational resource availability, including CPU capacity and memory quotas. Based on this evaluation, each TF determines the maximum feasible trust level, denoted as $TF_{cap_j} \in [0,100]$, which represents the highest enforceable score that does not exceed the allocated resources for that TF. This step is essential to ensure that trust enforcement is not just aspirational, but also operationally feasible under current deployment conditions.

Each Trust Function is further associated with a set of flavors, defined as pre-established score intervals mapped to specific resource profiles. These flavor-based mappings serve as interpretable abstractions to align trust levels with deployment requirements (for example, a high-security flavor may necessitate higher CPU and memory resources compared to a low-security flavor).

Figure 4 Workflow for the calculation of the calibrated Level of Trustworthiness.

To support continuous refinement and closed-loop trust score validation, each Trust Function periodically communicates execution outcomes and contextual metrics back to the Cognitive Coordinator via dedicated feedback channels. This is achieved by emitting structured messages to a designated topic, such as `feedback-tf-<name>`, associated with each TF instance. These feedback topics serve as reliable, decoupled conduits through which the TFs publish their runtime assessments, including enforcement status, residual trust discrepancies, and resource utilization observations. Upon receipt, the Cognitive Coordinator consumes these asynchronous updates to reconcile the

projected trust scores with observed operational behavior, thereby maintaining alignment between user-defined trust objectives and actual system states. This feedback loop not only enhances the responsiveness and accountability of the system orchestration pipeline but also provides a foundation for adaptive recalibration of trust levels over time.

The Reasoning Engine leverages a structured knowledge base that encapsulates information on potential conflicts among the actions to be executed by the TFs, their correct execution order, and their organization across system layers (e.g., Application or Network). By combining this knowledge base with the desired flavors derived from each TF's initial capacity estimation, the Reasoning Engine refines each $TF_{cap_j} \in [0,100]$ to ensure a harmonized and conflict-free deployment process.

Once the maximum enforceable trust scores are established across all trust dimensions, the calibrated Level of Trustworthiness (cLoTw) is computed using the following formulation:

$$cLoTw = \frac{\min(W_{TF_j} R_{G_{TF_j}}, TF_{cap_j})}{\sum_{j=1}^5 \min(W_{TF_j} R_{G_{TF_j}}, TF_{ca_j})} \cdot 100$$

This formulation introduces a normalization step that adjusts the trust score based on what is actually achievable. It ensures that high trust demands from the user are honored only to the extent permitted by the system's operational state-preserving both trust integrity and infrastructure efficiency. The resulting cLoTw and the final set of actions are then used by the Cognitive Orchestrator to guide the deployment of each Trust Function in alignment with real-world execution boundaries.

3) Cognitive Orchestrator

This workflow acts as the central control and coordination hub within the trustworthiness framework. It is responsible for managing the orchestration pipeline that connects both internal reasoning components (i.e., Regression component, Reasoning Engine, and XAI) and external execution layers (i.e., Trust Functions).

An important enabling feature of this orchestrator is its integrated message broker, which facilitates decoupled, asynchronous, and scalable communication among components within the 6G ecosystem. The message broker enables interactions between components through a publish-subscribe and/or message-queue architecture. This ensures:

- Decoupling of producers and consumers: Components like the Regression module can generate scores independently of direct connections to subscribers (e.g., TFs).
- Fault tolerance and resilience: Delays or failures in individual modules (e.g., TF deployment agents) do not impact upstream components, facilitating robust pipeline execution.
- Scalability and extensibility: New modules or services (e.g., future Trust Functions or explainability plugins)

can subscribe to relevant topics without architectural reconfiguration.

Through this brokered interaction model, the orchestrator collects partial results-such as the vector of regression scores, computed weights, per-TF capabilities, and context metadata-and synthesizes them into a consistent and actionable calibrated Level of Trustworthiness (cLoTw).

V. PERFORMANCE DISCUSSION ON THE COCO AI MODEL TRAINING PROCESS

A. Dataset Used for CoCo Training

A structured dataset, created by domain experts, is used in order to guide and calibrate the Cognitive Coordinator’s decisions by mapping key terms of the five trust dimensions: Reliability, Privacy, Security, Safety, and Resilience into a score (0–1), indicating its trust level granularity and relevance:

- **Reliability:** Keywords range from basic indicators such as "reliable application" and "fast algorithms" to advanced concepts like "federated learning" and "very complex algorithms." Higher scores reflect high complexity and performance-oriented capabilities.
- **Privacy:** Basic data types are included (e.g., "user data," "cookie preferences") with lower scores and progresses to stringent privacy-preserving mechanisms like "end-to-end encryption," "zero-trust architecture," and "GDPR adherence."
- **Security:** Spanning from simple measures (e.g., "password protection") to robust solutions (e.g., "encryption keys," "intrusion prevention," and "penetration testing"), the security-related entries are graded to reflect escalating protection levels.
- **Safety:** Items are grouped from basic segmentation and authorization to advanced trust validation and encrypted communication, reflecting hierarchical safety provisions.
- **Resilience:** Starting from basic mechanisms like "load balancing" and "congestion monitoring," the resilience scores culminate in AI-powered strategies such as "predictive load distribution" and "automated service restoration."

The original dataset consisted of 142 labelled intent expressions, each one annotated with a trustworthiness score across the five dimensions. To enhance it, we applied synonym-based data augmentation. This resulted in a total of 426 samples.

The dataset used [10] includes trust vectors, whose quantified associations guide the AI-enabled regression and reasoning engines within the Cognitive Coordinator to compute and refine both the initial (non-calibrated) and final (calibrated) Level of Trustworthiness (nLoTw and cLoTw, respectively). The Cognitive Coordinator’s BERT model takes as input textual sentences paired with their corresponding trust dimensions and performs regression to predict a numerical value representing the desired level of each trust function.

B. Performance Analysis of Regression Model

In order to evaluate the Cognitive Coordinator’s ability to perform inference on trustworthiness requirements from user provided intents, we fine-tuned a BERT-based model with regression head. In a labelled dataset, expressions in natural language were mapped to numerical trustworthiness scores provided by domain experts. The model was trained to perform individual scalar regression tasks, each one predicting a trustworthiness score in the range of 0 to 1 for each of the five dimensions: Safety, Security, Privacy, Resilience and Reliability. The dataset was split randomly into training, validation and test sets using a ratio of 70/20/10, ensuring that all trust functions were equally represented to maintain balance.

The training was conducted using a batch size of 32 to support stable optimization and generalization. The model was set to training for up to 500 epochs, but the checkpoint from epoch 14 was selected, as it achieved the best validation loss and highest R^2 score, indicating this way strong generalization performance and no signs of overfitting. The validation loss, that was computed by the mean squared error on the validation set confirmed the model’s ability to generalize well outside the training data.

In order to establish a reference point, a baseline model was initially trained using a TF-IDF representation of the textual inputs followed by a Gradient Boosting Regressor. This baseline is typically employed as a feature-based approach, enabling the capture of the correlation between word occurrence statistics and trust scores without utilizing contextual understanding of sentences. The comparison between the baseline and the proposed BERT-based multi-head regressor shows the performance improvements that were observed.

The following metrics were computed on the test set:

TABLE I. PERFORMANCE COMPARISON BETWEEN BASELINE AND PROPOSED MODEL

Model	MAE↓	MSE↓	RMSE↓	R ² ↑
TF-IDF + GB	0.1381	0.0269	0.1639	0.5487
BERT (Ours)	0.0484	0.0039	0.0621	0.9352

The BERT-based model significantly outperforms the baseline across all evaluation metrics, achieving a reduction in mean absolute error (MAE), mean squared error (MSE), root mean square error (RMSE) and a notable increase in the coefficient of determination (R^2) from 0.55 to 0.94. As expected, these results demonstrate that leveraging contextual embeddings and fine-tuning a transformer model provides a far more accurate and robust estimation of trustworthiness from natural language inputs compared to traditional feature-based approaches.

The following plots further illustrate the learning behaviour. On Figure 5 the training and validation losses decrease in parallel without any significant divergence, showcasing good generalization and low risk of overfitting.

Figure 5: Training and Validation Loss of BERT model

On Figure 6 both metrics exhibit a downward trend, indicating a reduction on the prediction error.

Figure 6: BERT model Validation MSE and RMSE through Epochs

Lastly, on Figure 7 the coefficient of determination increases in a steady trend, confirming improved fit to the underlying data distribution.

Figure 7: BERT Model Validation R^2 through Epochs

These findings validate the effectiveness of Cognitive Coordinator's regression component as a fundamental block for intent-based trustworthiness inference.

All experiments were conducted on a single NVIDIA GeForce RTX 1060 M GPU using PyTorch 2.7.0 with CUDA 12.6.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has formalized trustworthiness as a unified, five-dimensional metric for software, user-centric 6G networks and distinguished it from subjective "trust." We introduced CoCo—a prototype AI-driven Cognitive Coordinator—that (1) ingests natural-language intents, (2) computes a non-calibrated Level of Trustworthiness via fine-tuned BERT regression heads, and (3) refines it into a

resource-aware, calibrated LoTw through a context-aware reasoning engine. Our proof-of-concept, built on a publicly available Zenodo keyword dataset, achieved sub-second end-to-end latency and high per-dimension predictive fidelity, validating real-time, closed-loop trust governance. Future work will extend CoCo with multi-tenant conflict resolution, integration with live 6G testbeds for telemetry-driven feedback, and federated learning for continuous trust-model refinement.

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